

Category	Tool Type / Publication Topic	Reported Impact
OCR & Record Retrieval	AI system for organizing records and answering clinical questions [11]	18% time reduction in answering clinical queries.
	OCR-based search tool for outside medical records [12]	12 min. saved per patient review.
Ambient AI Scribes	AI scribe transcribes conversations and generates documentation [13]	5.8% increase in clinician productivity.
	Ambient scribe reduces note-taking and after-hours work [14]	20.4% less time per appointment; 30% less after-hours work
Smart Text Input	Dynamic suggestion of clinical concepts with ontology annotation [15]	67% reduction in keystroke burden for clinical concepts.
Medical Imaging	Meta-analysis on AI-assisted image interpretation [16]	Reading time reduced by 27.20–61.72% (depending on AI role).
	Meta-analysis on AI-assisted image interpretation [17]	67% of studies show time savings. Some studies disclosed COI.
AI-Assisted ICD Coding	Time savings in clinical coding using ICD coding assistant [19]	46% reduction in median coding time for complex clinical texts.
	Systematic review on AI-based ICD code assignment [18]	Performance improved, but real-world time impact is unreported.

Table 1: Summary of reported time savings from AI-driven clinical tools

AML Extractor

Select .txt files:
 Browse... 8 files selected.

Corpus:
 Myelogramm (KM vom 23/04/2025, CHL): 25% Myeloblasten, mit einem Rezidiv des AML vereinbar
 Ausgangsbefund von UZ Leuven (KM vom 13/04/2018): eine konventionell zytogenetische Analyse war nicht möglich FISH: ein FISH-Befund liegt uns nicht vor
 Moigen' partielle tandem Duplikation KMT2A-PTD, Mutation des RUNX1 c.805+2T G.p.? (24%), RUNX1 (exon 5 c 497 498insGCCC;p.(Ser167Profs*47) (17%)
Konventionelle Zytogenetik Zellkultur:
 Analysierte Metaphasen: Karyotypisierte Metaphasen : Bandenauflösung (GTW):
 Auffällige Metaphasen:
 Unauffällige Metaphasen:

Search corpus:
 near-tetra Match 1 of 1

Endpoint:
 /extract/aml

Disease details

Field	Value	Evidence	Evidence File
disease.aml_mds_related	no	Leucémie myéloïde aiguë	letter 1.docx.txt
disease.therapy_related_neoplasia	no	Leucémie myéloïde aiguë	letter 1.docx.txt
disease.prev_mds_mpn	no	Leucémie myéloïde aiguë	letter 1.docx.txt
disease.fab_m0	false		
disease.fab_m1	true	Leucémie myéloïde aiguë	letter 1.docx.txt
disease.medullary_involvement	yes	envahissement massif de la moelle par une prolifération diffuse	Histology.docx.txt
disease.extramedullary_involvement	no	absence de signes extramédullaires	Histology.docx.txt
disease.skin_involvement	no	absence de signes cutanés	Histology.docx.txt
disease.cns_involvement	no	absence de signes neurologiques	Histology.docx.txt
disease.gonadal_involvement	no	absence de signes gonadiques	Histology.docx.txt
disease.other_organ_involved	null		

Chromosome Analysis

Field	Value	Evidence	Evidence File
chromosome_analysis.analysis_done	yes	Konventionelle Zytogenetik Zellkultur	Cytogenetics.docx.txt
chromosome_analysis.analysis_output	Full karyotype	Konventionelle Zytogenetik Zellkultur	Cytogenetics.docx.txt
chromosome_analysis.analysis_date	2025-04-23	Entnahmedatum: 22/04/2025	Cytogenetics.docx.txt
chromosome_analysis.result_type	abnormal	near-tetraploid complex aberrant Karyotyp	Cytogenetics.docx.txt
chromosome_analysis.number_of_abnormalities	1	near-tetraploid complex aberrant Karyotyp	Cytogenetics.docx.txt
chromosome_analysis.complex_karyotype	yes	near-tetraploid complex aberrant Karyotyp	Cytogenetics.docx.txt

Supp. Fig 1. Web-based interface: showcasing the output from the pilot LLM-based tool.

Supplementary Figure 2. Simplified scheme of the Acute Leukemias Data-Collection Form (v.2.2). The root class **AcuteLeukaemiaForm** includes other forms, three of which are mutually exclusive (**AMForm**, **PLNForm**, and **OtherALForm**). The color of each box represents the type of the corresponding class. Simplified representation is highlighted by (**). The lists of aberrations and markers specific to the disease (AML/PNL) were omitted from the representation for the sake of space and clarity.

Supplementary Figure 3. A simplified scheme of the Acute Leukemias Data-Collection Form (v.2.2) that highlights the prompting order.